

Special Relativity, Energy and Measurement Part III

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From Maxwell's equations or from a Newtonian definition of work involved assembling charge on a conductor or creating a spherically charged object of finite radius, it is known that energy carried in electric E and magnetic fields B , is given by: $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} / \mu_0 B \cdot B$. In this note, we try to see if one may deduce the presence of energy in the E field without making use of the notion of work associated with assembling charge (or Maxwell's equations). In Part I, we called this a non-remeasurable type of energy. We argue here that the measurable is E , the electric field (and also B field)

We use the notion of the energy of a core charge Q with electrostatic potential ϕ interacting with a test charge q as having an energy $q \phi(r \text{ vector})$. We suggest that the potential energy maps directly into a change in the electric field because the one adds the fields of Q and q . We suggest that this idea may be extended to any change in the electric field being associated with energy. The electric field, however, is governed by a change in ϕ and A (magnetic vector potential) (4- vector) and it is this which dictates the new E field (and B) and hence the energy present.

We argue that the self-energy, i.e. the energy linked with an E field in the electrostatic case, is not a remeasurable quantity and that one must focus on the E field (and its link to ϕ). Thus, without the notion of work (associated with assembling the charge), this field self-energy does not necessarily transform according to a Lorentz transformation. The reason seems to be that E (and B) fields are constrained to be associated with the change in $(0, q\phi)$ to $(qAc, q\phi')$. No such constraint exists for a regular piece of rest mass or potential energy because it is not mapped to a changed E field. In other words, for an electrostatic charge, there exists a function $f(E \text{ vector}) = \text{scalar} = \text{energy}$, but it is the E vector which changes when viewed from a moving frame, not the function $f(E \text{ vector})$. E is an observable, while $f(E \text{ vector})$ is not. These ideas are an extension of Part I.

Electrostatic Interaction of Two Charges

One may consider the electrostatic picture of two charges Q, q separated by a distance L along the y axis. There exists a potential energy $q \phi$, where ϕ is the electrostatic potential energy of Q . In Part I, we argued that this energy was measurable and remeasurable and could serve as the fourth component of a 4-vector which transforms under a Lorentz transformation.

There is a second energy in the problem, namely the field self-energy $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E$, but we assume in this note that one does not know the existence of this energy. (In Part I, we argued that this was not a remeasurable energy.) Here, we consider the following idea. If charge q is held at a position L along the y axis from Q which is also fixed, it is not only the case that kinetic energy (part of mass energy) of q was converted into potential energy as it moved from $y = \text{infinite}$ to $y=L$ for Q at $y=0$, but the overall electric field present changes because one must add the electric field of Q to that of q . Thus, potential energy in this scenario maps directly to a changed electric field.

The argument we present is the following. Given that ϕ transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector:

$$(0, q\phi) \rightarrow (A, q\phi') \quad \text{where } A = qv \phi \text{ (vector)} \quad \text{and } q\phi' = q\phi / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((1))$$

$\phi'(r \text{ vector})$ should be written in terms of r' vector (i.e. the r vector as seen in the moving frame). Thus, the functional form of ϕ is changed not by the Lorentz transformation of ϕ , but by rewriting r vector in terms of r' vector. A changed ϕ' , however, implies a changed:

$$\text{Grad}' \phi' \quad ((2))$$

In the moving frame, $E = -\text{grad}' \phi' - d/dt' A$ ((3)), but we argue that it is enough that the $\text{grad}' \phi'$ piece is changed because the change is not compensated by $-d/dt' A$.

We argue that from ((2)), the E' electric field (seen in the moving frame) is different from that of a particle at rest. This result holds whether a q charge is present or not. We argued above, however, that a changed E field means a change in energy, thus we suggest that there must be an intrinsic energy associated with the observable E electric field.

It is interesting to note, however, that the E electric field does not transform under a Lorentz transformation. It is $q\phi$ which transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector. Thus, the transformation of $q\phi$ (and the emerging A) govern the form of the E and B fields seen in the moving frame

. If one does not associate a self-energy with E and B , then there is no issue. If one does, however, as argued above, then it seems as if there exists a contradiction because energy is supposed to transform as the fourth component of a 4-vector under a Lorentz transformation. The energy associated with the E (and B fields), namely $.5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ does not.

In Part I, we argued that such a Lorentz transformation does not apply because the self-energy is not a measurable and remeasurable one (at least not all of it). Here we suggest the same thing, but argue that this energy, in the case of the E field, is associated with the measurable, the E field. In other words, an electrostatic field has a self-energy:

$$\text{Scalar function } (E \text{ vector}) = .5 \epsilon_0 E \cdot E \quad ((3))$$

It is the E that is measured and one concludes that if E has changed, then the self-energy of ((3)) must have changed. E changes, however, according to the 4-vector (A, ϕ) . A person in moving frame does not see the self-energy and so there is no Lorentz transformation equation to write for it. It is measurable-remeasurables which are seen.

We argue that there is no contradiction because a usual Lorentz type energy is associated with the interaction $q\phi(Q)$, but this is automatically associated with a change in the measurable total E field. Thus, it is the E field which is a signature of a change in energy and the E field is measurable and remeasurable.

To reiterate what was argued above, one deals with a $q-Q$ system, but the transformation of $q\phi$ is really the transformation of ϕ by itself with no q present. A charge at rest has a different E field than one in motion even if one only considers $-\text{grad}' \phi'$. This change in E means an

associated change in an energy linked with E . Thus, even a charge at rest must have an energy associated with its E field, but it is the E field which is the measurable, not the energy. We argue that the Lorentz transformation acts on measurable quantities and so the self-energy associated fields $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} B \cdot B$ cannot be assumed, a priori, to be a measurable quantity and the Lorentz transformation should not be applied to it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one must be careful when stating that energy transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector under a Lorentz transformation. We argue that the quantities which transform as a 4-vector should be measurable and remeasurable. For example, $q\phi$ for an electrostatic charge transforms into $(Aqc, q\phi')$. A represents either the usual momentum associated with the energy $q\phi$, or is linked to a measurable B field = $\text{grad} \times A$ or an enhanced E field piece $-d/dt A$ partial. Self energy is associated with the creation of a charge and so is measurable once, but not remeasurable. It is the E field which becomes the measurable. The self-energy is no longer a measurable and so cannot a priori be used as the fourth component of a 4-vector in a Lorentz transformation. It is an energy which is manifested by an E field, while the rest mass energy is manifested by inertia. It is possible that some of the self-energy is in fact inertial, but a priori it does not seem that one knows how much.